

FOOD SAFETY AWARENESS AND ITS RELATIONSHIP TO PRACTICAL PERFORMANCE IN FOOD PROCESSING AMONG GRADE 10 LEARNERS AT BAMBANG NATIONAL SCHOOL

Remietania M. Ramos

*Nueva Vizcaya State University, Bambang, Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines
Bambang National High School, Bambang, Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19071659>

ABSTRACT

The study identified the relationship that exists between food safety awareness and practical performance in food processing among 30 Grade 10 students of Bambang National High School, school year 2025-2026. The study used a quantitative design, particularly descriptive-correlational. A researcher-made 40-item multiple-choice test was used for food safety awareness and a 20-item performance checklist for practical performance in food processing. The awareness test was on personal hygiene and sanitation, prevention of cross-contamination, proper power storage and temperature, and cleaning and sanitizing. Moreover, the performance checklist considered preparation and organization, food handling and safety compliance, processing and finished product presentation and quality. The level of awareness and performance was calculated by means and standard deviation and the correlation of the two variables at the level of significance of 0.05 was tested using Spearman rank-order correlation. The results showed that the respondents were very aware of food safety ($M = 20.77$, $SD = 2.487$). Personal hygiene and sanitation, proper food storage and temperature control, and cleaning and sanitizing were found to be highly aware whereas cross-contamination prevention was rated low. Learners had shown a good level of performance ($M = 3.03$, $SD = 0.260$) in all the dimensions. The findings did not indicate any significant correlation between food safety awareness and practical performance (0.238 , $p = 0.206$). This implies that the level of awareness does not always result in effective practical performance in food processing activities.

Keywords: *food processing, food safety awareness, practical performance*

INTRODUCTION

Food safety is a vital life skill that safeguards the health of the people and provides an assurance that foods are safely prepared and consumed. In the case of young learners, the knowledge of good hygiene, prevention of contamination, and safe food handling would make them realize their involvement in keeping safe and healthy. By instructing the learners on how to make food as well as handling it safely, this makes them more responsible persons in the prevention of foodborne diseases. Nevertheless, food safety education has not gained much attention in classrooms, nor has it been regarded as an essential life ability, but is in some cases considered only as a technical skill.

Across the world, the issue of food safety has gained a lot of importance since food supply chains have increasingly been complexing with the increase in cases of foodborne diseases. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), millions of individuals fall ill of foodborne diseases annually and more food safety education and prevention approaches should be put in place (WHO, 2006). Strengthening food safety systems and food safety awareness are also emphasized by international organizations like the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) as ways to reduce health risks and to make the food handling practices safe (FAO, 2003). The research also demonstrates that the enhancement of food safety knowledge and practices among people is a significant control in the prevention of foodborne illnesses (Young et al., 2022).

A number of researches have emphasized the role of food safety education in students. Indicatively, in a research study by Taneja et al. (2020), the researchers determined that despite many students having basic information on food safety, their food handling behaviors were weak in most cases, thus the need to continuously learn and educate them. Equally, a study of college students found that they had knowledge gaps concerning cross-contamination prevention, correct food preparation methods, and temperature control, which means they should teach students better food preparation methods (Sirsat et al., 2024). These outcomes indicate that despite the level of awareness, it might not be enough to ensure safe food handling behavior without adequate training and application.

The establishment of the Food Safety Act of 2013 (Republic Act No. 10611) in the Philippines reinforced the national policies to ensure that consumers are not exposed to food safety hazards. Nevertheless, food safety education has not been integrated well in basic education. Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) is a subject where students acquire knowledge on how to prepare and process food, but the concepts of food safety are poorly conveyed. Due to this, the learners might learn how to cook but fail to learn the significance of sanitation practices, hygiene practices, and practices on the control of contamination (Department of Education [DepEd], 2016).

Learners in Bambang National High School in Nueva Vizcaya are involved with food processing as a part of TLE curriculum. Nevertheless, observations in the classroom show that learners are not equally aware of and practicing food safety. Other learners show little knowledge in regards to sanitation, hygiene, and contamination control,

whereas others face a challenge in adhering to safety protocols at all times when performing practical tasks. The teachers have also complained of restricted availability of localized teaching aids that can effectively incorporate food safety concepts in the TLE lessons.

Based on these issues, this research study sought to establish the degree of food safety knowledge and practical performance among Grade 10 students in food processing. It further analyzed the presence of a meaningful association between the food safety awareness and performance of the learners.

Research Questions

1. What is the respondents' level of awareness on food safety along personal hygiene and sanitation, cross-contamination prevention, proper food storage and temperature control, and cleaning and sanitizing?
2. What is the learners' level of practical performance in food processing along preparation and organization, food handling and safety compliance, processing techniques, and presentation and quality of finished product?
3. Is there a significant relationship between respondents' food safety awareness and their practical performance in food processing?

METHODOLOGY

Quantitative research design was utilized, particularly descriptive-correlational study to establish the level of food safety awareness and practical performance on food processing among Grade 10 students of Bambang National High School. The quantitative design was employed to achieve objectivity and minimize bias in data collection and analysis whereas the descriptive-correlational method was employed to establish the relationship between the food safety awareness of the learners and their results in the practical food processing tasks.

The study respondents were a sample of 30 out of 41 Grade 10 learners in the TLE-Food Processing classes in the school year 2025-2026. Simple random sampling was used to select the participants. Ethical considerations like informed consent, voluntary participation and confidentiality were adhered to.

Data collection was done using two research instruments. The first tool was a 40-item multiple-choice test crafted by the researcher on food safety awareness using the guidelines of the World Health Organization (2006), National Restaurant Association (2020), and Department of Education Food Processing curriculum (2016). It addressed four aspects, which included personal hygiene and sanitation, prevention of cross contamination, appropriate food storage and temperature control, and cleaning and sanitizing. The second tool was a 20-item performance checklist that was used to

evaluate the practical performance of the learners in food processing. The checklist was based on Food and Agriculture Organization (2003), TESDA, National Restaurant Association (2020), and Department of Education Food Processing curriculum (2016), including preparation and organization, food handling and compliance, methods of processing, and presentation and quality of a finished product. The two instruments were expert validated and piloted.

Mean was employed in the analysis of the data in order to find the level of food safety awareness and practical performance by the respondents. The use of Spearman rank-order correlation (Spearman rho) was to test the relationship between the two variables because the data were not normally distributed as it was confirmed by the Shapiro-Wilk test ($p = 0.014$). The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1. What is the respondents' level of awareness on food safety along personal hygiene and sanitation, cross-contamination prevention, proper food storage and temperature control, and cleaning and sanitizing?

Table 1
Respondents' Level of Awareness on Food Safety

Food Safety	Mean	SD	QD
Personal Hygiene and Sanitation	5.27	1.258	High
Cross- Contamination Prevention	4.93	1.048	Low
Proper Storage band Temperature Control	5.27	0.944	High
Cleaning and Sanitizing	5.30	1.179	High
Overall	20.77	2.487	High

Qualitative Description (QD) per Domain: Very High (7.50-10.00); High (5.00-7.49); Low (2.50-4.99); Very Low (0.00-2.49)

Overall Qualitative Description (QD): Very High (31-40); High (21-30); Low (11-20); Very Low (0-10)

The findings show that the respondents in general had a High awareness on food safety ($M=20.77$, $SD = 2.487$). This means that learners have a fairly sufficient knowledge of food safety procedures, which is important in the prevention of foodborne diseases and safe food preparation processes, particularly in food processing activities in schools.

Cleaning and Sanitizing got a high mean score ($M = 5.30$, $SD = 1.179$), which was followed closely by the Personal Hygiene and Sanitation ($M = 5.27$, $SD = 1.258$), and Proper Food Storage and Temperature Control ($M = 5.27$, $SD = 0.944$). Nevertheless, Cross-Contamination Prevention received the lowest average score ($M = 4.93$, $SD = 1.048$), which means that the gap in knowledge of students is significant.

This trend indicates that the learners could be familiar with overall hygiene and cleanliness standards but not familiar with technical and procedural standards to avoid

contamination by improper handling, use of utensils, and raw and cooked food separation. This may be a significant implication since cross-contamination is one of the key factors in the outbreak of foodborne diseases, especially in household and school-based food preparation.

The results indicate the existence of a gap in the learning resources that can enhance food safety education especially on the areas demanding procedural knowledge and critical judgment when preparing food. Other researchers have stressed the need to reinforce food safety awareness among young learners with a systematic training and context-based teaching to make them apply their food safety awareness to safe food practices (Baptista et al., 2020; Young et al., 2022).

Research Question 2. What is the learners' level of practical performance in food processing along preparation and organization, food handling and safety compliance, processing techniques, and presentation and quality of finished product?

Table 2
Respondents' Level of Practical Performance in Food Processing

Food Processes	Mean	SD	QD
Preparation and Organization	3.25	0.291	Good
Food Handling and safety Compliance	3.00	0.263	Good
Processing Techniques	2.95	0.406	Good
Presentation and Quality of Finished Product	2.93	0.365	Good
Overall	3.03	0.260	Good

Qualitative Description (QD): Very Good (3.50-4.00); Good (2.50-3.49); Fair (1.50-2.49); Needs Improvement (1.00-1.49)

The result shows that the respondents displayed an overall Good level of practical performance in the process of food processing as depicted by the overall mean score of 3.03 (SD = 0.260).

The greatest dimension in terms of mean was Preparation and Organization with the highest mean (M = 3.25, SD = 0.291), with Presentation and Quality of Finished Product having the least mean (M = 2.93, SD = 0.365). In spite of the results pointing to an overall ability of the learners to execute the tasks related to food processing in a sufficient way, the lack of ratings with the label of Very Good implies the possibility of the improvement, especially in terms of the technical skills and the quality of the product.

These results suggest that even though learners already have the background in the preparation of food, their skills might still need the improvement to attain the next level of performance. In food processing, practical performance not only entails knowledge but also psychomotor skills, procedural accuracy and stable implementation of food safety principles. The studies underscore that practical learning experiences and disciplined

training in terms of skills enhance the cooking abilities and performance rates of learners to the significant level (Kim & Ham, 2021; Pendergast et al., 2020).

The findings also indicate that food safety awareness may not necessarily result in excellent practical performance. This explains why instructional resources that support the gap between theoretical learning and practical application in terms of experiential learning and competency-based learning are required.

Research Question 3. Is there a significant relationship between respondents' food safety awareness and their practical performance in food processing?

Table 3
Relationship between Food Safety Awareness and Practical Performance in Food Processing

Variables	df	ρ	p-value	Remark
Food Safety Awareness and Practical Performance in Food Processing	28	-0.238	0.206	Not significant

The results show that food safety awareness does not have a significant relationship with food processing practical performance. Accordingly, the null hypothesis is accepted.

This finding means that food safety awareness does not always guarantee an increase in the practical performance of learners. Although the level of awareness and good level of performance was high among the learners, knowledge will not necessarily guarantee skill mastery. The cognitive domain, which is food safety awareness, and the practical performance, which involves psychomotor skills, regular practice, and procedural accuracy, are necessary.

This observation is consistent with the recent findings which suggest that more food safety knowledge does not necessarily translate into a better food handling behavior unless it is reinforced by experiential and hands-on training (Bou-Mitri et al., 2020; Young et al., 2022). The literature on competency-based education also highlights that technical skills are acquired in the form of supervised practice, feedback, and performance-based evaluation as opposed to theoretical knowledge alone (Kim & Ham, 2021).

The fact that there is no meaningful correlation implies that raising awareness might not raise the practical competencies of the learners. Thus, the suggested learning content must combine cognitive teaching with guided laboratory work, demonstrations, and performance assessment aids, to enable the knowledge gap and application to be addressed properly.

Conclusions

Considering the results of the research, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The Grade 10 students of Bambang National High School exhibited high awareness on food safety in regard to personal hygiene and sanitation, food storage and correct temperature, cleaning and sanitizing. Nonetheless, the awareness level among learners regarding the prevention of cross-contamination was low, which means that this area of the food safety is a weak point that should be improved with the help of increased learning abilities and instruction.
2. The respondents had good level of practical performance in food processing with regards to all dimensions. Even though their performance could be generally discussed as satisfactory, as the results show that learners have not yet achieved a very good level of competence, it means that they still need to improve their skills and use more organized performance-based learning activities.
3. The food safety awareness of the respondents did not have any significant relationship with their food processing practice. This means that knowing or understanding of food safety principles does not guarantee effective application during actual food processing activities. Thus, food safety education must not be limited to the awareness only, but must also put an emphasis on practice training, regular monitoring, and the application of the skills.

Recommendations

The research findings and conclusions provide the following recommendations:

1. Given that the respondents demonstrated high awareness in most of the areas of food safety and low awareness in the prevention of cross-contamination, the teachers of the TLE may conduct more specific training on the risks and prevention of cross-contamination. Learning activities in the form of scenarios, practical demonstrations and visual presentation may be combined to enhance the awareness and perceptions of learners. Moreover, the discussion of food safety issues may be periodically reinforced by classroom reminders and laboratory regulations to reveal the appropriate use of the safe practices.
2. The teachers may offer more practical training and more frequent performance-based activities to reinforce the technical skills of the learners. Processing techniques and presentation and quality of final products can be developed through the application of performance rubrics, guided practice and teacher feedback. School administrators may as well make sure that there are sufficient equipment and materials required in effective food processing teaching.
3. As no strong correlation between the food safety knowledge and the practical performance was observed, the teaching methods may be concentrated on the gap

between the knowledge and the application of skills. Educators may use competency-based learning strategies with focus on practice training and real demonstration of food safety practices. In the laboratory operations, continuous monitoring and evaluation may also be done to check whether food safety principles are fully exercised and observed.

4. Further researchers may perform similar studies through bigger sample and incorporate more schools in order to enhance the generalizability of the results. They may also look at the correlation between the practical performance of the learners with the other variables that are connected to this like age, gender, academic achievement, food safety awareness and study habits and their participation in food preparation activity.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher followed ethical standards by securing authorization to conduct the study, obtaining informed consent, and practicing voluntary participation. The respondents were informed of their rights including their data privacy. There was also no conflict of interest. Plagiarism and AI used were strictly avoided.

Acknowledgments

The author acknowledges the respondents for their time and participation as well as the Nueva Vizcaya State University and Bambang National High School.

REFERENCES

- Baptista, R. C., Rodrigues, H., Sant'Ana, A. S., & Lemos, M. (2020). Consumer food safety knowledge, attitudes, and practices: A systematic review. *Food Control*, 109, 106907. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2019.106907>
- Bou-Mitri, C., Mahmoud, D., El Gerges, N., & Jaoude, M. A. (2020). Food safety knowledge, attitudes and practices of food handlers in Lebanese hospitals: A cross-sectional study. *Food Control*, 94, 78–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2018.06.032>
- Department of Education. (2016). *Technology and livelihood education: Food processing curriculum guide (Grade 10)*. Department of Education.
- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. (2003). *Assuring food safety and quality: Guidelines for strengthening national food control systems*. FAO.
- Kim, S., & Ham, S. (2021). The effects of culinary education and training on students' cooking competence and food safety practices. *Journal of Culinary Science & Technology*, 19(4), 295–310. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15428052.2020.1790941>
- National Restaurant Association. (2020). *ServSafe coursebook (7th ed.)*. National Restaurant Association.
- Pendergast, D., Garvis, S., & Kanasa, H. (2020). Insight into food literacy and its development in school education. *International Journal of Home Economics*, 13(1), 4–18.

- Republic of the Philippines. (2013). Republic Act No. 10611: Food Safety Act of 2013. Official Gazette.
- Sirsat, S. A., Sirsat, T. S., & Madera, J. (2024). College students' domestic kitchen food safety perceptions and knowledge. *Journal of Food Science Education*.
- Taneja, N., Malhotra, N., Shankar, R., Pal, A., Ahmed, S., Awasthi, A. A., & Janardhanan, R. (2020). A study on knowledge, attitude and practice on food safety and hygiene among the students of a private university of Delhi NCR. *Journal of Nutrition Health & Food Science*.
- Technical Education and Skills Development Authority. (n.d.). Food processing NC II training regulations. TESDA. <https://www.tesda.gov.ph>
- World Health Organization. (2006). Five keys to safer food manual. World Health Organization.
- Young, I., Thaivalappil, A., Waddell, L., Meldrum, R., & Greig, J. (2022). Psychosocial and organizational determinants of safe food handling at retail and food service establishments: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(3), 1190. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19031190>